

“FOOD AND BEVERAGE DEPARTMENTS OF HOTEL”

Abdurasulova Mekhribon

“Food and beverage departments of hotel”

Tashkent 2024

Abstract: In fact, hotels have served as a hostel for the night since time immemorial. Today, hotels have changed not only accommodation, but also all services. There are many hotels in the world and We only know the most luxurious ones, so hotels are awarded stars based on their capacity and service they provide to customers. International hotels are cheaper and more developed than hotels in Uzbekistan, and their customer service is still at a high level. In our article, we have explored the most prestigious international hotels and hotels in Uzbekistan and we conducted questionnaires with clients.

Key words: hotels, hotel classification, international hotel service, Hotel service in Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION

To this day, hotels serve as temporary housing. Previously, they were built in 2-room apartments. But today they not only serve as a place of temporary residence, but in addition there is a dining room, entertainment clubs, bars, ceremonial halls for weddings and events, conference rooms for scientific and business conferences. In large hotels, if there are all types of services, then in small hotels there are some types of services. Usually small hotels provide only accommodation and meals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Food and beverage presentations in moodle system 2023
- Food and beverage service by John Cousin 1996
- BEST PRACTICES IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANAGEMENT Judy A. Siguaw and Cathy A. Enz 1996
- Google

- Restaurant concepts, management and operations. Eight edition John R.walker
2018)

BODY PART

Most define a hotel as a temporary home away from home provided by a business that specializes in offering private room accommodations. However, the reasons for seeking hotel services are numerous. A person may choose to stay at a hotel as part of a vacation or retreat. A business person may need to stay at a hotel when travel is required for their job. A hotel room may also be necessary for someone between homes or whose home is uninhabitable due to renovations or damage. Hotels fall into a number of classes based on the different types of services they provide and the quality of the accommodations. In addition to having a wide selection of hotels from which to choose, hotel patrons must also consider their room preferences. The hotel industry is a prominent player in tourism and business, thus, its impact on a country`s economy is significant. Many people are employed in the hotel industry and hold roles either at the “front of the house” or the “ back of the house”. The entire operation requires savvy hotel management. Hotel management involves a fine-tuned orchestration of a hotel`s property and employees. Hotel departments often include reservations , housekeeping, food and beverage, sales and marketing. Given the complexities of the job, hotel management is a career that requires extensive training. Both associate and bachelor`s degree programs are available for the specific field. In discussing the ways that hotel organizations have changed, we pointed out that in earlier times food played a significant role in the organizational structure and product/ service mix of hotels. It has been speculated that the preeminent role played by hotel foodservice in society became significantly diminished with the onset of Prohibition and during the 1920s. People stopped going to foodservice establishments where they couldn`t “get a drink.” Prohibition gave rise to competition from street restaurants that operated sub rose as speakeasies. These restaurants were not constricted by the visible, public nature of hotel dining rooms. This diminished role was compounded in many ways by the depression years of the 1930s and the war years of the 1940s. The organization of

foodservice departments within lodging establishments varies depending on the type of facility and, in the case of chain operations, corporate policies. Due to this degree of variety, categorizing lodging properties can be difficult. For example, a property located in a resort environment may also have extensive convention space. A property known primarily as a convention hotel has room enough to accommodate large. In most kitchen operations, an executive chef is responsible for management related to production activities. Depending on the size and complexity of the operation, the executive chef may actually perform little in the line of food production. In a small operation, the chef may also be a part owner and perform most of the food-related functions. One of the exciting trends today is the use of big name chefs in hotel food services, often allowing them to create a signature room in the lodging property. The proper positioning of the restaurant in a niche market can also have a residual positive effect on average rate and occupancy. Marketing a celebrity chef as a primary component of a hotel may yield a competitive advantage among that specific hotel's competitive set. With the trend toward downsizing operations, it would be the rare organization in lodging foodservice that employed numerous back-of-the-house employees engaged in a single function. Some examples of the past might include the sous-chef, the executive chef's assistant and often the staff supervisor; the saucier, or sauce cook; the cook in charge of all cold food preparation; the chef patissier, or pastry chef; and the banquet chef in charge of catering. Each of these positions would have had assistants. In addition, other jobs were steward, purchasing manager, storeroom clerk, and several janitorial staff. Hotels are complex institutions divided into separate operational areas, among them rooms, engineering, administrative, accounting, human resources, and sales, in addition to continually in contact with food and beverage units, particularly room service, to request special arrangements for their clients. These requests might range from amenities being delivered and set up in the guest room to supplying the gaming area with special foods and drinks. The type of client sleeping in the guest rooms significantly affects the revenue-generation potential of a lodging food and beverage operation. Because a majority of food and beverage customers may be

hotel guests, it is important to book the right type of people into the hotel. The sales mix of the hotel is a delicate balancing act. Sales staff must make sure they are contracting groups that maximize hotel revenue per available room.

(Food and beverage presentations in moodle system 2023)

Every hotel employee is a sales agent for the property’s food and beverage outlets. The staff must be trained to refer and recommend hotel services to guests. It is clear that the quality of food and beverage operations can affect overall hotel operations and profitability. Quality is particularly important for convention hotels and resort hotel properties. Guests come to such properties for specific purposes. Therefore, a reputation as a high quality food and beverage operation will attract customers. These operations generate word-of-mouth advertising from travel agents, corporate meeting planners, cab drivers, airline companies, and tourism offices. While this reputation can attract guests, it is the responsibility of management to plan effectively for their needs. Imagine you run a hotel restaurant, operate room service, provide food and beverages for employees, and now are also catering several types of meals/functions for different groups. Recall that the goal of the hotel property is to service its clientele. Therefore, each area of the hotel must complement the other in providing the service.

The international foodservice industry provides millions of meals a day in a wide variety of types of operation. 1 Food can include a wide range of styles and cuisine types. These can be classified by country, for example, traditional British or Italian; by type of cuisine, for example, oriental; or a particular speciality such as fish, vegetarian or health food. 1 Beverages include all alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks. Alcoholic beverages include wines and all other types of alcoholic drink such as cocktails, beers and cider, spirits and liqueurs. Non-alcoholic beverages include bar beverages such as mineral waters, juices, squashes and aerated waters, as well as tea, coffee, chocolate, milk and milk drinks and also proprietary drinks such as Bovril.

(Food and beverage service by John Cousin 1996)

Organizing job functions in Hotel Food and beverage department first of all organized Food and beverage director – management all of restaurant services and

workers (BEST PRACTICES IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANAGEMENT Judy A. Siguaw and Cathy A. Enz 1996)

Food and beverage manager —Coordinates and directs the entire operation to assure efficient quality, courteous foodservice. Works through supervisory personnel, but in smaller restaurants may directly supervise kitchen and dining room staffs. Must know all of the details involved in every restaurant job. A food and beverage director in a major lodging property must be ready for a variety of tasks each and every day. In one sense, this position requires two different individuals to keep the operation moving forward. One is the leader, or strategic visionary, looking ahead to the future of the operation (that may be just one or three months, or it could be one full year out). The other is the day-to-day manager, constantly moving through the organization to be sure all events are proceeding according to plan and guests are treated beyond their expectations. In this position, I have the responsibility of overseeing several departments: culinary, banquets, room service, specialty and theme restaurants, and all private bars. While an ideal day is spent on planning, more often than not I find myself in discussion with staff or guests. Regular meetings include the following examples:

- (Daily) Banquet Event Orders (BEO) Meeting. Purpose: To go over BEO for the day.
- (Weekly) Food and Beverage Meeting. Purpose: Review operations with department managers.
- (Weekly) Executive Meeting. Purpose: Overview operations with all executive committee members and the general manager of the hotel.
- (Weekly) One-on-One Meetings. Purpose: Meet with individual food and beverage departmental managers to establish goals and cover issues specific to each department.
- (Monthly) Staff Meeting. Purpose: Review operations by all department managers and general manager of the hotel.
- (Monthly) Employee Recognition Meeting. Purpose: Honor employees of the month at a luncheon. To gain a better appreciation of the job of a director of food and

beverage, we should look at an actual job description. Again, recognize that all job descriptions are written as an ideal, and every day brings deviations from that ideal, given the unique daily circumstances found in any dynamic lodging property. I am expected to perform special projects as requested and to maintain a high level of professional appearance, demeanor, ethics, and image of subordinates and myself. Part of our culture in this hotel concerns professional development of staff associates, and it is among my responsibilities to find ways to provide for this. As you can see, the job of a hotel food and beverage director requires a high-energy person who loves working with people in a variety of dynamic situations. The ability to lead a group of employees in pursuit of operational goals is paramount. Students should actively seek experiences in their college career that provide opportunity to learn the skills mentioned in this article.

ASSISTANT MANAGER—Performs specific supervisory duties under the manager’s direction. Generally takes over in the manager’s absence. Must be thoroughly familiar with the entire operation and have good management skills.

FOOD PRODUCTION MANAGER— Responsible for all food preparation and supervision of kitchen staff. Must have thorough knowledge of food preparation and good food standards. Should know how to work with and supervisor people.

DINING ROOM MANAGER— Coordinates dining room activities, trains and supervises host/hostess, waiters, waitresses, busboys, and busgirls. Should possess leadership qualities, objectivity, and fairness.

ROOM SUPERVISOR—Orders, receives, inspects, and stores all food for distribution to the different food departments. Must be capable of managing an inventory and keeping track of current market prices. This job is sometimes the responsibility of the manager or chef.

CASHIER—Receives payment for food and beverages sold. May total checks. Must be personable, quick at mental arithmetic, and completely.

PANTRY SUPERVISOR—Supervises salad, sandwich, and beverage workers. Should be able to create attractive food arrangements. May be in charge of requisitioning supplies and supervising cleaning crew.

HOST/HOSTESS—Takes reservations. Keeps informed on current and upcoming table reservations. May present menu and introduce waitperson. Should be attractive, friendly, able to maintain composure when restaurant is busy.

WAITER—Supervises and coordinates activities of dining room employees, performing in a formal atmosphere. May be responsible for scheduling hours and shifts, keeping employees' time records, and assigning work stations.

BEVERAGE WORKER—Prepares hot beverages such as coffee, tea, or hot chocolate. May assist in the pantry and help others in the kitchen during rush hours.

(BEST PRACTICES IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANAGEMENT Judy A. Siguaw and Cathy A. Enz 1996)

The bar manager or beverage director is the person who makes it all happen in relation to hotel beverages. Although specific responsibilities may vary from one hotel to another, the fundamental role of the manager is to make certain that the five basic functions of management are applied effectively. As in many other business sectors, these are planning, organizing, directing, staffing, and controlling. The wise and competent bar manager applies and adapts the fundamental principles of each of these functions to the specific needs of the operation. All five functions are determining factors in meeting the operation's ultimate objective: profitability. It all begins with planning and continues in directing and organizing so that the staff on a daily basis diligently adheres to the established standards. Examples: checking bartenders' opening and closing duties, standardizing drink recipes, verifying that the bar par stock (established amount of beverage product) is at the proper level, scheduling, forecasting, frequently communicating with other fellow managers (in particular the catering manager and the executive steward), and so forth. The competent bar manager always finds sufficient time to inspect the underbars (the working area behind and underneath the bar counter), the jockey boxes (the small compartment next to the ice bin), and the

speed racks (where the inexpensive, or well, bottles and the more popular brand-name liquor are placed). The above are also the areas where managers cannot place enough emphasis on how vital it is to the operation to continuously apply sanitary standards and practice the utmost cleanliness. Glassware must not only be cleaned but sanitized as well. An important organizational and training function is the sequencing of beverage stock. This is the order in which spirits and cordials are placed on the shelves or speed rack. It also refers to the order by which the drinks are called to the bartender by the serving staff, and it must always be the same. Supervising the beverage staff and ensuring that control methods are foolproof are crucial and demanding tasks; sequencing provides part of the structural mix that helps assure consistency of product and service.

(BEST PRACTICES IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANAGEMENT Judy A. Siguaw and Cathy A. Enz 1996)

Organization Chart of Beverage Department in a Medium to Large Hotel

General Manager, Hotel Food and Beverage Director Assistant Beverage Manager (Head Bartender) Beverage Manager.

Long working hours are the norm in restaurants. Some people like this; others get burned out. Excessive fatigue can lead to general health problems and susceptibility to viral infections, such as colds and mononucleosis. Many restaurant operators have to work 50 hours or longer per week, too long for many people to operate effectively. Long hours mean a lack of quality time with family, particularly when children are young and of school age. Restaurant owners have little time for thinking—an activity required to make the enterprise grow. In working for others, managers have little job security. A shift of owners, for example, can mean discharge. Although restaurant owners can work as long as the restaurant is successful, they often put in so many hours that they begin to feel incarcerated. Family life can suffer. The divorce rate is high among restaurant managers for several reasons. Stress comes from both the long hours of work and the many variables presented by the restaurant, some beyond a manager's control. One big challenge for owners is the possibility of losing their investment and

that of other investors, who may be friends or relatives. Too often, a restaurant failure endangers a family's financial security because collateral, such as a home, is also lost. Potential restaurateurs must consider whether their personality, temperament, and abilities fit the restaurant business. They must also factor the economy into the equation. New restaurants are always opening, even in a failing economy. New restaurant owners can count on the fact that, even in a bad economy, people still have to eat. Consumers are mindful of how they spend their hard-earned money, and restaurant dining is a part of discretionary income, meaning people will spend first on essentials and then on niceties such as dining out. They may trade down and dine at quick-service or casual restaurants instead of using fine-dining restaurants. (Restaurant concepts, management and operations. Eight edition John R. walker 2018)

METHODOLOGY

As a result of research and preaching, we discovered and answered various questions: 1. About the age of visiting tourists 2. How many tourists visit hotels in Uzbekistan about 3. About whether they are satisfied with the hotel services of Uzbekistan and vice versa 4. What is the opinion of Tourists visiting Uzbekistan about hotels in Uzbekistan 5. about whether you like or dislike the services of hotels in Uzbekistan 6. About whether or not they visited other countries besides Uzbekistan 7. About Tourists' opinion about large hotels in foreign countries 8. About the importance of local residents in the further development of hotels in Uzbekistan 9. We collected answers about Measures for the further development of tourism in Uzbekistan different opinions and discussions about the possibility of implementation PARTICIPANTS AND DATA COLLECTION Examples were taken at the "Courtyard by Marriott" hotel in Tashkent and at the "Hilton" hotel, located on the city square of Tashkent city, cafes, bars, restaurants, in Tashkent International Airport, Uzbekistan Railways. The sources in the article are taken from various Literature and from various Internet sites. An electronic form of a questionnaire that was conducted jointly with researchers through social networks and messengers were sent to the respondents. There were 9 questions in the questionnaires, and 35 tourists took part in this.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the answer to the first question, the majority of tourists in the questionnaire are 30-35 years old. To our second question, almost 41% of tourists answered that they visited Uzbekistan for the first time and saw the services of hotels in Uzbekistan for the first time. We found out that 67.7% of tourists are satisfied with the hotels in Uzbekistan. 32.3% of tourists reported that they were not satisfied. According to our fourth question, 35.5% of tourists rated Uzbekistan hotels as satisfactory. 51.6% of tourists rated our hotels well, 12.9% of tourists rated hotels are in very good condition. It turned out that 48.4% of tourists liked the hotel service of Uzbekistan, and 51.6% of tourists did not like it 80.6% of tourists who visited other countries compared the conditions of the hotel service in Uzbekistan and the service of other foreign countries 61% of tourists called the condition of foreign hotels very good, 19% of tourists were satisfied 19% of tourists rated it better. On the negative impact of the local population on hotels in Uzbekistan in 29% of cases” answered “no”, in 71% of cases they answered “yes”. In order to further develop tourism in Uzbekistan, 80% of tourists received various answers and suggestions. The table below shows the percentage of tourists who are satisfied with hotels in Uzbekistan displayed as number In the table, the assessment of tourists who visited hotels in foreign countries in numbers and percentages

RECOMMENDATION

According to the recommendations of tourists who took part in the survey Further development of tourism activities in hotels in Uzbekistan

- Improving service,
- improving the culture of local residents,
- Paying attention to the design of hotel equipment It is necessary to improve the knowledge of local tourists about the norms of the law Development of the tourism system

- Need to work in HR
- Create broad opportunities

REFERENCERS

1. (rooms Division Operations by Contributors (z-lib.org) 2021)
2. (rooms Division Author Collective Operations (z-lib.org)2021)
3. (www.google.com)
4. (I.f.n. – R.S. Amriddinova, Nurullayeva Y. 2015)
5. (http://www.worldtourism.org/wiki/Category:Marriott_International_brands)
6. <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/13gYhljxSFzfuu0iN2XnghmGtzcDWbjejNg6uBlmJ7A/edit?chromeless=true>